

Research paper

Computational fluid dynamics investigation of wave interactions with damaged coastal cliffs

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ABSTRACT

Numerous studies have documented that increasingly intense weather and climate events are amplifying marine wave activity. However, complex links between oceanic storms and coastal environments require further investigation to assess risk and develop effective mitigation strategies. Although past studies have focused on various coastal structures, this one investigates extreme wave impacts on a Mediterranean Sea cliff hosting cultural heritage sites. Advanced two-dimensional computational fluid dynamics models were developed for a range of solitary wave heights and cliff geometries. Unlike previous studies, the work herein considers a key natural feature, namely basal notch, caused by progressive cliff damage under the wave action. Three sea cliff types are considered: an undamaged cliff, one with a submerged and one with a partially submerged notch. The hydrodynamic interactions of waves with cliffs are investigated both qualitatively and quantitatively, focusing on flow patterns, wave runup and cliff exposure. The CFD results reveal that partial damage, i.e., notch, generally reduces the maximum wave runup but increases the water retention time on cliffs, especially in the submerged notch case. For the largest wave, the submerged notch reduces maximum runup by 10% but increases retention time by 70%, increasing internal weakening probability. Additionally, although the horizontal velocity of water along undamaged cliffs is negligible (-0.006 to 0.004 m/s), the presence of a notch can amplify it to about -6 to 4 m/s under a 2.0 m wave, potentially altering the flow patterns and the dominant damage mechanism. Overall, the study highlights cliff geometry as a critical factor in wave vulnerability.

1. Introduction

How the occurrence of very intense weather and climate events can lead to a significant increase in the intensity of marine waves has been reported in several studies. While extreme wave events are already frequent in many regions, projections suggest that more intense wave storms will occur under high-emission climate scenarios, with coastal wave energy flux expected to increase by 30 % in parts of the Southern Hemisphere by the end of the century [1]. In a corroborating manner, satellite observations from 1985 to 2018 show that extreme wave heights (90th percentile) have increased by approximately 1.0 cm/year in the Southern Ocean and 0.8 cm/year in the North Atlantic [2]. Even considering a longer period, studies show that global wave power has risen by an average of 0.47 % per year from 1948 to 2008 and reaching up to 2.3 % per year since 1994 globally, closely linked to climate-driven

wind changes [3]. These high-energy frequent events threaten not only built infrastructures—such as ports, seawalls, and coastal defenses—but also trillions of dollars in coastal assets and over 10 % of the global population residing in low-lying coastal zones [4]. This vulnerability becomes more critical when such coastal areas host important infrastructure or valuable cultural assets. This concern is exemplified in Ventotene Island (Italy) (Fig. 1), where an eroding volcanic cliff borders and supports several cultural heritage (CH) sites, such as the “Villa Giulia” Roman Imperial palace. The cliff is highly susceptible to landslides, which accelerate the coastal retreat process and therefore poses a significant threat to the preservation of the archaeological site as recently highlighted by cliff failure events and monitoring activities conducted within the TRIQUETRA project [5], which have led to the realisation of the Ventotene Field Laboratory (<https://dst.web.uniroma1.it/index.php/it/ventotene-field-laboratory>).

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Fig. 1. (a) Geographic location of Ventotene Island, Punta Eolo promontory, and the Villa Giulia CH site; (b) detail of the Villa Giulia CH site; (c) plunging cliff at Punta Eolo showing overhangs and notches (red box) and the sub-vertical geometry of the cliff.

Sea waves impact represents one of the most important controlling factors in coastal cliff dynamics [6]. There are several studies that have confirmed the vulnerability of coastal cliffs to high wave conditions. Sallenger et al. [7] observed cliff retreat of up to 14 m along the California coast during the 1997–1998 El Niño winter, which was closely associated with periods of repeated wave arrival at the base of the cliff. This suggests that an important destructive factor is the duration when the cliff is exposed to water which aligns with Palmsten and Holman [8] findings that had shown the length of exposure to waves to be nearly as important as knowing the details of water level for modeling dune erosion. Moreover, since natural cliffs always have cracks and fractures with porosity, the exposure time (water elevated on the cliff) is expected to become more important in the long run and make the sea cliff more vulnerable to the wave-induced erosion.

Hansom et al. [9] suggest that steep waves of 10 m or more impacting a 15 m high cliff can produce sufficient impact pressure to promote crack propagation, block detachment, and uplift of large blocks as various modes of damage. More recently, Shen et al. [10] drew attention to another common coastal cliffs damage. They conducted flume experiments to study damage that progressively develops at the base of a cliff due to swash abrasion and found that notch erosion rates exceeded 2 mm/hr and is controlled by vortex location and uprush height. Seeking quantification of such cliff erosion, Alessio and Keller [11] showed that erosion is exacerbated during high-energy wave events, particularly when wave energy flux exceeds threshold conditions near the cliff toe. In a similar effort, Bergillos et al. [12] modeled wave exposure along the Spanish coast and found that the most vulnerable areas received peak wave power more than 13 kW/m². In this way, Young et al. [13] assessed over 4000 erosion events along the California cliff line using high frequency lidar monitoring and confirmed that wave impact at the cliff base was the primary driver of short-term retreat, reaching up to 2.74 m over 3 years of the study period in hotspots. The erosion rate is also a function of wave-cliff hydrodynamic interactions: The steeper and more reflective beach in front of a cliff, the greater the wave run-up and resulting cliff erosion. This was confirmed when Earlie et al. [14] showed that the volume of erosion over a one-year period was twice as high at a reef site facing a reflective beach (1.1 m/year) compared to a dissipative beach (0.5 m/year).

Since there is a wide range of studies on wave-structure interaction

and hydrodynamics, mainly targeting runup, overtopping, hydrodynamic loads, and design of coastal barriers and dunes [15,16], decks and jetties [17,18], elevated buildings [19] and other structures, research has progressed to the point where it now deals with structures beyond conventional ones with innovative designs. For example, Heidarzadeh et al. [20] developed a predictive relationship for wave runup on a novel high-strength steel mesh cover, and Moss et al. [21] used physical modelling to show that novel rock-bag revetments effectively reduce it. In contrast, despite all the efforts mentioned above, natural systems such as sea cliffs have been relatively underexplored.

Previous studies have improved our understanding of wave-induced erosion on coastal cliffs via (a) numerical and physical experiments focusing on simplified geometries and typically representing them as vertical walls or (b) site-specific observations [22,23]. However, this paper aims to depict a picture of the extent of hydrodynamic exposure on more irregular cliff shapes with a basal notch, motivated by the analyses conducted for the sea cliff of Punta Eolo promontory in Ventotene island in the framework of the Horizon Europe TRIQUETRA project. Shedding light on this topic is crucial for advancing research on rocky coast analysis, particularly in terms of slope stability and coastal erosion processes. This is especially relevant given the limited current understanding of the mechanical role played by wave action in controlling coastal stability. Therefore, the objective of the present research is to advance the understanding of extreme waves interaction with notched coastal cliffs by examining both the flow dynamics within the notch and the spatial distribution of cliff exposure and runup on the cliff. This is achieved via high-fidelity, multi-phase computational fluid dynamics modeling with Large Eddy Simulation (LES) turbulence sub-models, which considers three different shapes of the cliff and a range of solitary waves that are commonly used to simulate long-period, high-energy events such as storm surges and meteo-tsunamis (e.g., [24–26]). Although idealized, solitary waves are widely adopted as the canonical long-wave model for tsunami-like coastal events, because they capture the fundamental hydrodynamic processes that govern runup and impact including long wavelength, weak dispersion, and strong shoreward momentum [27]. Despite the limitations of this idealized formulation, solitary waves remain applicable for studying long-wave coastal processes, particularly within the range of $H/h < 0.5$ [28].

Fig. 2. (a) Bathymetric and aerial DTMs of Punta Eolo used to extract (b) aerial and (c) underwater swath profiles.

2. Study site description

Ventotene is a volcanic island located about 50 km off the Italian west coast. The tuffaceous lithology of the sea cliffs makes the entire island perimeter highly prone to erosion, thereby enhancing coastal retreat and increasing the susceptibility of the cliffs to landslide processes [29]. These phenomena are threatening the preservation of the TRIQUETRA project pilot site of the Roman Villa Giulia in Ventotene island, which is located on the promontory of Punta Eolo [30].

The promontory of Punta Eolo in Ventotene island is characterized by steep cliffs that plunge below the sea level, forming vertical or semi-vertical faces that can be classified as “plunging cliffs”, following the classification of Sunamura [31]. Despite their vertical shape, rocky cliffs of this type exhibit morphological irregularities, including overhangs and basal notches. The genesis of these asperities is controlled by the geomechanical setting of the rock mass, as well as by the erosional action exerted by the sea-waves impact. These characteristics make the Island of Ventotene particularly relevant for investigating how natural cliff geometry interacts with wave activities over time. The longevity and safety of these CH assets remain closely tied to the structural condition of the cliff and its response to repeated severe sea states.

The importance of studying the effects of marine weathering on a sea cliff like the one in Ventotene, from the perspective of possible climate change scenarios, lies in the fact that these morphological elements are among the first to register the effects of global climate variations (even compared to inland glacial systems), since they can be jointly affected by variations in the intensity of thermal stressors (such as air temperatures), which can alter the mechanical properties of rocks, as well as variations in the frequency and intensity of atmospheric and marine storm events.

2.1. Cliff geometry and bathymetry

High-resolution digital terrain models (DTMs) derived from bathymetric and aerial surveys have been used to represent sea bathymetry

and cliff geometry accurately. In particular, the western sector of Punta Eolo was analyzed because i) it is the area exposed to the highest waves, which, in Ventotene, predominantly come from the west, and ii) no detailed bathymetric data are available for the eastern part of the promontory. The bathymetry was provided by the municipality of Ventotene and was obtained using multibeam and single beam echosounders and achieved a spatial resolution of 10 cm, even in areas close to the coastline. The aerial DTM was generated from a drone-based photogrammetric survey with a ground sampling interval of 0.89 cm, providing important details of the investigation area. These DTMs were processed in MATLAB using the TopoToolbox program [32]. The elevation values of the DTMs were extracted along predefined transects oriented perpendicularly to the cliff, considering a width of 250 m for the aerial sections and 300 m for the underwater sections, respectively. The processed swath profiles allowed the calculation of statistical parameters (e.g., minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation of elevation) across the swaths, providing a realistic representation of the 2D cliff and seabed morphologies. In particular, the swath analysis carried out on the bathymetric data revealed seabed depths ranging from about 4 m below sea level (b.s.l.) near the cliff to approximately 16 m b.s.l. in the offshore zone, over a horizontal distance of ~450 m. On the other hand, by considering the aerial swath profile, it is clear that the aerial cliff face has different slopes at different sections, which affects the total hydrodynamic effects of the wave on the cliff [33]. For the purposes of numerical modeling, the cliff can be reasonably idealized as a vertical geometry, which adequately represents the local morphological setting (Fig. 2b). Field evidence reveals that the sea slopes at Punta Eolo are also shaped by overhangs and notches (Fig. 2c). These morphologies can potentially influence the hydrodynamics of the sea waves on the cliff by affecting the flow around and within the cliff. In the study area notches and overhangs come in a variety of heights and widths, reaching up to 7 m and 2 m, respectively. To clarify, we're going to examine one of the largest and one of the smallest cases to better understand the process and its impact, which is more distinct compared to intact or slightly damaged cases.

Fig. 3. wave rose diagram illustrating dominant wave directions in the study area.

2.2. Wave characteristics

Wave characteristics are another local factor that determines the nature of hydrodynamic interactions in a region. In this study, we extracted the wave climate in the region through data from an open-source database. MetServices uses the WaveWatch III model to provide wave condition forecasts and hindcasts for the Mediterranean Sea and forces the model with high-resolution wind fields from the CFSR (Climate Forecast System Reanalysis) to realistically reproduce the wind and swell wave components. According to Fig. 3, a wave height of 4 m is the highest wave that is likely to occur, and we set it as the upper bound for our study.

Fig. 3 also shows that sea waves predominantly originate from the west, confirming that the assumption of a 2D CFD model is valid when considering waves approaching from the west and impacting the western cliff of the Punta Eolo promontory.

3. Computational framework

As mentioned above, there is a need to carefully investigate the flow conditions around pre-damaged coastal cliffs, especially those with a notch at the base. The best way to capture this complex hydrodynamics is to use high-fidelity mesh-based computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models. In this study, we are using OpenFOAM v2406, an open-source CFD platform capable of resolving highly dynamic wave fields [34], to simulate wave interactions with the damaged cliff geometry under a wide range of solitary wave heights. The solver is based on the finite volume method (FVM), in which the entire computational domain is discretized into control volumes and solves the governing equations of the fluid motion over each volume. Boundary conditions are also applied at all domain boundaries, and fluxes are evaluated across the faces of the control volumes.

The sub-solver used in this study is interFoam, the multiphase flow solver of OpenFOAM, that uses the Volume of Fluid method (VOF) for tracking the air-water interface and estimating the fluid surface changes. In this method, the free surface between two immiscible phases is tracked by moving a scalar field that represents the volume fraction of one of the fluids within each computational cell. Then, all governing equations are updated at each time step over the entire domain leading to accurately modeling the transient behavior of the wave interaction with the structure.

3.1. Governing equations and solver

According to Newton's second law, the amount of force acting on an object is equal to the rate of change in its momentum:

$$F = \frac{dP}{dt} \text{ \& } P = mu \rightarrow F = \frac{d}{dt}(mu) = m \frac{du}{dt} + u \frac{dm}{dt} \xrightarrow{\text{if } m \text{ is constant}} F = ma \quad (1)$$

Where P is the momentum of the object, u is the velocity vector, and m is the mass, but in terms of fluid mechanics, the mass is defined as the product of the fluid density ρ and the differential control volume dV that yields ρdV . So, we modify the first equation as below:

$$P = \rho dV \cdot u \rightarrow \frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\rho dV \cdot u) = \rho dV \cdot \frac{Du}{Dt} \quad (2)$$

Provided that ρ is constant. Since OpenFOAM is a Eulerian framework, acceleration term is expanded as follows:

$$\frac{Du}{Dt} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, F , the total force exerted on the differential control volume (dV), comprises various force components that are acting within the fluid:

- Pressure force: a force created by pressure difference inside the fluid. ($-\nabla p$, it is negative as the pressure difference makes a force in the opposite direction)
- Viscous force: this type of force is the result of internal friction in the fluid, resisting relative motion between adjacent fluid layers. For a Newtonian fluid, this force is proportional to the velocity gradient ($\mu \nabla^2 u$)
- Gravitational force (ρg)

Finally, the Navier-Stokes equations are derived by applying Newton's second law to fluid motion, replacing each term with expressions appropriate for fluid particles:

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 u + \rho g \quad (4)$$

Turning dynamic viscosity (μ) to kinetic viscosity (ν) we will have:

$$\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u \right) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \nabla^2 u + g \rightarrow \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 u + g \quad (5)$$

When large eddy simulation (LES) is the turbulence modeling method, there is a key change to this equation. This method solves large eddies (turbulent eddies) in a flow using a computational grid until a threshold where the eddies are called sub-grid scale and must be modeled using an empirical equation. This is where the effective viscosity term is defined in the NS equation to account for smaller eddies (artificial viscosity).

$$\nu_{eff} = \nu + \nu_t \rightarrow \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + (\nu + \nu_{eff}) \nabla^2 u + g \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\nu_t = C_k \cdot \Delta \cdot (k)^{0.5} \quad (7)$$

k is the turbulence kinetic energy which is obtained by solving this equation:

$$ak^2 + bk + c = 0, \text{ where:}$$

$$a = \frac{C_e}{\Delta} \quad (8)$$

$$b = \frac{2}{3} tr(D) \quad (9)$$

Fig. 4. Depiction of model used in the validation study based on Chan and Street [39].

$$C = 2C_k \Delta (\text{dev}(D) : D) \quad (10)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla u + \nabla(u)^T) \quad (11)$$

And Δ is the filter width below which the turbulence is being modelled instead of solved.

Furthermore, the continuity equation must always be solved alongside the Navier-Stokes equation to ensure mass conservation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \quad (12)$$

And if the fluid is incompressible:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \rightarrow \nabla \cdot u = 0 \quad (13)$$

Due to the multiphase flow, where interface tracking is handled by the VOF method, another governing equation is introduced and solved alongside the other equations in the entire domain. This is called the VOF transport equation.

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha u) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha(1-\alpha)u_r) = 0 \quad (14)$$

where α is a coefficient from 0 to 1, representing a completely air cell to a completely water cell, respectively. The first term represents the local (unsteady) change, which describes how the fluid velocity distribution changes over time at a point. The second term is the convection term, which describes how the fluid moves with the flow field. The last term is called the compression term, which is an artificial term to sharpen the interface.

u_r is an artificial compression velocity that points normally to the interface, with magnitude proportional to the flow speed and is obtained from Eq. (15):

$$u_r = C_{interface} \cdot \|u\| \cdot \hat{n} \quad (15)$$

where:

$C_{interface}$ is a user defined coefficient usually between 0 and 1.

$\|u\|$ magnitude of the velocity field.

$\hat{n} = \frac{\nabla \alpha}{|\nabla \alpha|}$; unit normal to the interface.

The momentum equation is always used to control the fluid motion, and the continuity equation ensures the conservation of mass. However, this study is a two-phase flow simulation and therefore we use the interFoam solver which also considers the transport equation to track the water surface. In addition, the governing equations are also dependent on the turbulence model as they include a turbulence term as a force in the flow that affects its motion. This study employs LES-Smagorinsky method, which introduces a modification to the Navier-Stokes equations, as shown in Eq. (6).

3.2. Numerical schemes and solver settings

Each of the governing equation terms are estimated using FVM method in each cell. The time derivative called the transient term, which shows how velocity is changing with time at a fixed point, is reliably

solved by first-order Euler scheme that supports nonlinearities in wave propagation. In order to discretize the gradient term (gradScheme), Gauss theorem is applied considering linear interpolation that provides second order accuracy and good convergence characteristics. Convective term in the momentum equation is discretized by linearUpwind scheme, enhanced by velocity gradient to improve accuracy when there are sharp flow variations.

The transport equation that tracks the water surface is handled by two diverging terms. The transport of volume fraction field α is performed using Gauss vanLeer, providing a second order accuracy that preserves a smooth interface during wave propagation. Then to counteract numerical diffusion and ensure a sharp transition between the fluids, an artificial compression term was applied through the Gauss interFaceCompression scheme, which operates only near the water surface.

This solver uses the PIMPLE algorithm, which combines the PISO and SIMPLE methods and is suitable for transient and incompressible multiphase flows. The outer loop uses a single corrector while the pressure-velocity coupling is done using two inner correctors (nCorrectors = 2).

In this case, we use MULES (Multidimensional Universal Limiter for Explicit Solution) to solve the VOF transport equation, which leads to an accurate solution of the phase interface as it ensures the volume fraction is always between 0 and 1. The solver uses one alpha correction (nAlphaCorr = 1) and three sub cycles (nAlphaSubCycles = 3) to maintain the clarity and numerical stability. An interface compression coefficient $C_\alpha=0.2$ applied to suppress spurious interface wiggles and maintain a more stable free surface during intense wave impacts, while avoiding the rapid growth of wiggles reported when stronger compression values are used [35]. A Boussinesq-type wave was generated at the inlet with active absorption enabled, while a shallow-water absorption was imposed at the outlet boundary which is located on the top the cliff. Turbulence is modelled using LES with Smagorinsky sub-grid model, where the default Smagorinsky constant is applied ($C_k=0.094$, $C_e=1.048$) and the filter width is calculated based on the cube-root cell volume. Near solid boundaries, the nutkWallFunction is used as the near-wall treatment, placing the first cell in the logarithmic region of the boundary layer.

3.3. Validation study

Model validation, based on comparison with benchmark cases or real-world data, is an essential step in mathematical modelling prior to applying numerical methods to coastal engineering problems [36].

Despite being inherently 3D, LES models have been proven accurate in 2D simulations that involve solitary wave propagation and hydrodynamic impact on coastal structures [37,38]. To evaluate the simulation results presented in this study, a validation study has been conducted based on the experimental study done by Chan and Street [39]. This experiment involves solitary waves running up on a vertical wall where the bathymetry is horizontal, as shown in Fig. 4. The same configuration was adopted and the maximum runup was measured under different wave height as shown in Fig. 5. The comparison of the

Fig. 5. Maximum runup instance when a 4.0 m solitary wave hits a vertical wall located on a horizontal bed.

Fig. 6. Normalized runup predicted by 2D CFD-LES model of present study and the experiments of [39].

non-dimensional runup acquired from the present study simulations against the experiments, shown in Fig. 6, reveals the high accuracy of the 2D CFD model with LES, with a difference less than 1% for the smallest and 5 % for the largest wave.

4. Model configuration and sensitivity analyses

Although the Navier–Stokes equations and the OpenFOAM framework are inherently three-dimensional, the present study considers a Newtonian air–water system and normally incident solitary waves interacting with a laterally uniform vertical cliff and bathymetry. In this configuration, the dominant hydrodynamic processes, including shore-normal momentum flux and impact, free-surface evolution, runup, and jet formation, remain predominantly two-dimensional; therefore, the simulations in this study are two-dimensional and realistically depict the impact of solitary waves of varying heights on different cliff geometries. However, this assumption does not account for spanwise water motion, vortices, or three-dimensional turbulence that may develop when waves encounter sharp corners or irregular features, nor does it represent the finite alongshore extent of a real notch, which could allow lateral recirculation in a fully three-dimensional flow. On the other hand, the model is designed with sufficient spatial extent to allow wave generation, propagation, impact, and reflection from the cliff without interfering with the boundary conditions or making its duration sub-optimal. Last but not least, it is noteworthy that although studies of wave on cliffs are very limited, a two-dimensional assumption is commonly accepted in coastal engineering and a plethora of studies have used 2D CFD for investigating the wave impact on coastal structures, like wave interaction with low-mound breakwaters validated with experimental tests [40], irregular wave impact on permeable structures [41], seawall erosion due to wave impact on vertical structures in Arctic coastline conditions [42], solitary wave impact on decks [43], tsunami borne debris impact on vertical structures and bridges [44,45] and dam-break

Fig. 7. Schematic side view of the numerical tank showing the mesh zoning for the undamaged cliff case (dimensions in meters).

Table 1
wave gauges locations within the computational domain.

Wave gauge number	Location (m)
WG1	50
WG2	100
WG3	110
WG4	120
WG5	130
WG6	140
WG7	150 (Run-up)

wave propagation on composite bathymetries [46]. As shown in Fig. 7, it represents a simplified bathymetry based on the site surveys that include a horizontal part of 100 m followed by an 8 % slope starting at $x = 100$ m. At the end, the cliff is located at $x = 150$ m. The water depth is 8 m offshore and 4 m at the cliff location while the cliff height is 28 m. In addition, there is a 10 m space above the cliff to let water inundate the top of the considered sea cliff.

Fig. 7 shows that the domain is divided into 5 meshing grading blocks to achieve more flexibility in representing various cliff geometries and adapt with different configurations. This also allows more precise control over mesh size in different regions to improve computational efficiency. The most important mesh region that dictates the entire domain grid size starts from 1.5 m below to 12 m above water level and includes the 2nd and the 3rd regions. They are the primary area of interest where the wave propagates, and impacts happen. It is located around the cliff and the notch, handling the most intense hydrodynamic interactions. This region received the finest mesh while the

upper and lower regions, where flow doesn't exist or remains relatively uniform, a coarser mesh was assigned. The spatial discretization is done through blockMeshDict, which is the internal structured mesh generator of OpenFOAM. For all cases, a three-layer boundary layer is added on the cliff and notch faces to place the first cell at approximately $y^+ \approx 300$, improving the resolution of velocity gradients and capturing wave impacts on the cliff. This is especially necessary when the model is using the VOF method coupled with LES turbulence modeling. The mesh is made parallel to the slope after the horizontal part to minimize the numerical diffusion during wave runup and impact.

To ensure a correct wave propagation throughout the domain and to analyze the wave's hydrodynamic changes, seven wave gauges are placed, as listed in Table 1. The first gauge is located 50 m from the inlet boundary on the horizontal part to confirm correct wave generation and approach toward the cliff. The second gauge is positioned at the beginning of the slope, while the seventh measures run-up on the cliff. The other wave gauges are evenly spaced along the slope at 10 m intervals.

As displayed in Fig. 8, the notch is located at the base of the cliff, precisely at its intersection with the seabed. Two types of notches are adopted to be studied: a submerged notch and a partially submerged notch, where the H_N is variable (3 m in submerged and 6 m in partially submerged case) and W is fixed at 1.5 m.

Inside the notch, six vertical lines (stations) are defined along which the water velocity and level are measured. The first line is located 0.25 m inside the cliff, and the others are distributed 0.25 m apart. The last line is located adjacent to the back wall of the notch.

In accordance with Fig. 7, Fig. 9a shows regions 1 and 2, which

Fig. 8. Schematic view of the two notch configurations: (a) Submerged notch and (b) Partially submerged notch (Numbers are in meters).

Fig. 9. Meshing details around the cliff and the notch region: (a) Notched cliff and (b) Undamaged cliff.

Table 2

Mesh sensitivity study cases used for evaluating wave propagation and run-up performance.

number	Wave Height (m)	Cell Height (cm)	Cell Length (cm)
1	0.5	3.3	6.7
2	0.5	5.0	10
3	0.5	10.0	20
4	2.0	3.3	6.7
5	2.0	5.0	10
6	2.0	10.0	20
7	4.0	3.3	6.7
8	4.0	5.0	10
9	4.0	10.0	20

together form the notch zone. Region 1 has a fixed height, ends at 6.5 m above the seabed, and provides a smooth transition from the sloped bathymetry into the notch, avoiding any abrupt change in the mesh and congestion at the end of the slope that could distort the wave entry path. Region 2 height is variable depending on the notch height. Above the notch, region 3 starts from the notch and extends vertically up to 20 m elevation from the seabed and captures the full splash and runup zone. Regions 2 and 3 form the impact zone.

In contrast, regions 4 and 5 are placed above the impact zone and aren't involved in the hydrodynamic processes, so, a coarser grid is used to reduce computational cost. For the undamaged cliff case (Fig. 9b), region 1 ends at the top of the slope, and since there is no notch, regions 2 and 3 are merged to form a continuous block. This mesh configuration provides non-skewed mesh at the impact zone around the cliff, yielding more accurate results.

4.1. Boundary conditions

The computational domain is bounded by boundaries dictating the model behavior. Inlet is the boundary where the generated solitary wave enters the domain and starts propagating toward the other end. This is set as (alpha.water: waveAlpha, U: waveVelocity, p: fixedFluxPressure, nut: calculated). This Inlet provides the velocity and surface profile required to initiate solitary wave propagation in equilibrium with pressure based on the flow rate. At the other end, the cliff is modeled as a solid wall, similar to the seabed, and enforces no-slip velocity and impermeable boundary condition (alpha.water: zeroGradient, U: noSlip, p: fixedFluxPressure, nut: nutkWallFunction). However, there is an Outlet border above the cliff defined as (alpha.water: zeroGradient, U: waveVelocity, p: fixedFluxPressure, nut: calculated). This boundary permits both phases to exit and enter the domain that minimizes artificial reflection since it attenuates gradients and pressures while waves pass through. The upper boundary of the domain is set as (alpha.water: inletOutlet, U: pressureInletOutletVelocity, p: totalPressure, nut: zeroGradient) that simulates free atmosphere, allowing air to move in and out, while preventing any inflow of water. Since the simulations are two-dimensional, the side boundaries are assigned the 'empty' boundary condition, meaning that the solver does not compute equations in the third dimension.

4.2. Mesh sensitivity

A sensitivity analysis on the mesh was carried out, as summarized in Table 2, to identify the most appropriate grid resolution that balances computational cost and accuracy. The mesh configuration focuses on the central region of the domain, where wave propagation and cliff impact occur. In this region, three different mesh densities were tested, referred to as fine, medium, and coarse meshes.

For the fine mesh, the core cell size was set to 3.3 cm in the vertical direction (z) and 6.7 cm in the horizontal direction (x), yielding an aspect ratio of approximately 2. In the region beneath the impact zone, the vertical resolution was matched to the horizontal one (6.7 cm) to

preserve isotropy and maintain numerical stability. Above the impact region, where vertical flow motion dominates due to wave splash-up and runup, the vertical cell height was increased to 10 cm, which is suitable for resolving steep upward jets. For the medium mesh, the core vertical resolution was increased to 5 cm, with a corresponding horizontal size of 10 cm. The mesh layers below the impact zone had a height of 10 cm, and those above were extended to 15 cm, maintaining a vertical stretching ratio greater than one. In the coarse mesh configuration, the core vertical resolution was 10 cm with an aspect ratio of 2. Both the upper and lower surrounding regions used a consistent vertical spacing of 20 cm to avoid excessive grid coarsening while preserving adequate resolution near the cliff.

To improve spatial accuracy near the cliff, local mesh refinement was applied in the vicinity of the notch and along the cliff surface. Specifically, the mesh was refined in the horizontal direction up to 1.5 m from the cliff, where cell size was halved. Vertically, refinement was also applied from the impact zone upward the same way to better capture reflection, jetting, and water motion. The refined region spans the full height of the notch when there is a notch as we expect more intense variations in the hydrodynamics.

The selected core cell heights of 3.3 cm, 5 cm, and 10 cm were chosen based on the smallest incident wave height (H), yielding resolution of $H/15$ (i.e., fifteen elements per wave height), $H/10$, and $H/5$, respectively.

Mesh sensitivity is examined in terms of wave propagation and runup on the cliff for three different wave heights: small, medium, and large. Fig. 10 demonstrates a great correlation between the medium and the fine mesh resolution, with differences of $<3\%$, which provides sufficient confidence to proceed with the next stages.

4.3. CFL sensitivity

Another important factor influencing the accuracy of the simulations is the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number. To ensure numerical stability and temporal resolution, the time step must be sufficiently small so that the fluid motion is accurately captured as it is traversing from one cell to the next. If the CFL condition is not met, the solver may advance the solution too far in time, bypassing important flow updates and leading to numerical inaccuracies.

$$N_{CFL} = \frac{U\Delta x}{\Delta t} \quad (16)$$

Instead of employing a constant time step, we adopted a variable time-stepping strategy, where the time increment is dynamically adjusted during the simulation to maintain the CFL number below a predefined threshold. This ensures that the field is precisely resolved throughout the domain and that no critical phase of the water motion is missed. For this step, two wave heights, the smallest and largest, are considered with the medium mesh. This sensitivity study is conducted according to Table 3.

Fig. 11 shows the wave evolution and the runup on the cliff in different cases. Even though the smaller time step size does not contribute to the accuracy of the model when the wave height is only 0.5 m, however, it has a critical role when the wave is larger and steeper.

In the 4 m wave height simulations, the medium-CFL case closely matches the finest one. Consequently, the final computational domain, including the model setup and spatial and temporal discretization, is selected based on sensitivity studies that confirm adequate convergence while optimizing computational cost. This is achieved by the medium-mesh model with a $CFL=0.5$.

5. Results and discussion

This section reports the results of the numerical simulations designed to investigate the flow transformation around various sea cliff geometries subjected to solitary waves. The analysis is structured to combine both qualitative and quantitative insight into water behavior. First, we

Fig. 10. Mesh sensitivity study for different wave heights: (a) $H = 0.5$ m, (b) $H = 2.0$ m, and (c) $H = 4.0$ m. The left column shows water surface variations at 50 m from the inlet boundary, the middle column at 135 m, and the right column presents the run-up on the cliff.

Table 3
CFL sensitivity study cases for different wave heights and medium mesh resolution.

number	Wave Height (m)	Cell Height (cm)	CFL (cm)
1	0.5	5.0	0.2
2	0.5	5.0	0.5
3	0.5	5.0	1
7	4.0	5.0	0.2
8	4.0	5.0	0.5
9	4.0	5.0	1

employ a series of visualizations to perceive how water starts running up the cliff and getting back based on velocity field in the impact zone. These visual observations provide essential context for understanding the underlying physics, showing key mechanisms of run-up, flow redirection, and potential vulnerability zone. Then, we transition to quantitative evaluations using time-series and comparative plots that assess run-up height, duration, and exposure metrics.

In addition to run-up, this research delves into velocity patterns on the cliff face and inside the notch that proves there are other unnoticed mechanisms that impose substantial threats to the structural integrity of

Fig. 11. CFL sensitivity study for wave heights: (a) $H = 0.5$ m and (b) $H = 4$ m. The left column shows water surface variations at 50 m from the inlet boundary, the middle column at 135 m, and the right column presents the run-up on the cliff.

the cliff. In the end, it is clarified how notch geometry and wave characteristics influence the cliff's exposure to flow dynamics, offering a more complete basis for vulnerability assessment under extreme marine conditions.

5.1. Cliff inundation visualization

This section provides an explanation about the hydrodynamic behavior around different cliff types through a series of velocity field snapshots. These images help to understand the evolution of velocity during key stages of the cliff inundation and wave run-up, from initial wave approach to peak of run-up and subsequent recession for all three geometries. This visual analysis highlights key flow patterns, such as water jetting, circulation within the notch, and differences in wave climbing behavior, which are critical in understanding the fluid dynamics across the tested configurations. The emphasis here is to perceive the dynamic nature of the flow and to reveal the localized behavior that may exacerbate the cliff exposure.

Fig. 12 visualizes how the vertical velocity component varies during the wave-cliff interaction in all three cliff configurations for a 2.0 m wave. Each row shows representative moments in three key stages: the initiation of run-up, the moment of maximum run-up, and the run-down phase from left to right. The undamaged cliff exhibits a sharp upward jet with a velocity of about 2.1 m/s that leads to the peak runup height at 21.5 s in a relatively short time span (~ 3.5 s) when the flow starts to reflect from the cliff and then runs down with a maximum velocity around 1.6 m/s. This behavior is characteristic of direct momentum reflection on a vertical face. In the submerged notch case, the key events

happen at the same time as in the previous case. However, the flow velocity increases during the run-down phase to 2.0 m/s, indicating a contribution from the circulating water being pushed out of the notch.

Fig. 12c, which corresponds to the partially submerged notch, demonstrates a much higher velocity field in the run-up phase, around 8.5 m/s, after the wave hits the sharp corner of the notch and makes a remarkable jet toward the top of the cliff. That's why the peak run-up height happens very fast and only 1 s after the wave impacts the sea cliff. The velocity of water while returning is about 30 % higher in this case and as the run-up height is smaller, the run-down phase decreases to about 3 s. Overall, the presence of a notch not only redistributes the incoming momentum but also slightly alters the run-up process as the local flow dynamics near the base of the cliff undergoes significant changes.

As expected, a 4.0 m wave exhibits more substantial differences in vertical velocity patterns as shown in Fig. 13. In the undamaged cliff, high particle velocities up to 8.3 m/s make the water reach the highest point in less than 2 s and when getting back, a bigger run-down velocity of about 9.7 m/s is observed. This event spans approximately 9 s, capturing a very short but intense phase of converting kinematics to potential energy. The submerged notch case shows a similar behavior to 2 m wave height but vertical motion velocity during run-down grows up to 11 m/s, which is about 10 percent this time.

The partially submerged configuration exhibits the most dramatic upward jet, with the highest velocity almost 17 m/s in the near field around the notch external corner. This vertical motion is very fast that peaks the water in 1.5 s and recesses rapidly in 2.5 s. This time the return velocity is about 8.6 m/s, lower than the submerged case. This can be

Fig. 12. Vertical velocity field for a wave height of 2.0 m impacting different cliffs: (a)Undamaged cliff, (b) Submerged cliff, and (c) Partially submerged cliff. For each panel row, the distance scale is uniform in both spatial directions.

attributed to the larger wave fully filling the notch, preventing water particles from draining downward. The contrasting flow structures underscore the role of notch geometry in reshaping wave energy into vertical motion, particularly under extreme wave loading.

According to Fig. 14, the horizontal velocity pattern reveals how the flow approaches the cliff base in different configurations. In the undamaged cliff, the incoming wave starts climbing the cliff while the horizontal velocity is around 2 m/s. It creates a big circulation upon reflection after the maximum run-up occurs, as large as the wet area on the cliff that results in a small negative velocity. This recirculation region at the base dissipates as the wave retreats by 28 s. In the submerged

notch case, the water is already circulating inside the notch when the wave starts to run up and clearly shows how the wave energy is being trapped. This circulation continues even until the recession is complete. The flow remains relatively stable and sheltered in this notch, so the water velocity is almost constant inside the notch during the process and is about 1 m/s, forming a relatively confined, horizontal vortex. The partially submerged case displays turbulence within the water, as both positive and negative velocities appear in a small region at the front of the water stream ascending the cliff. At the instance of maximum run-up, the water begins to reflect. At this stage, a void forms just above the external corner of the notch, with a vortex developing below and

Fig. 13. Vertical velocity field for a wave height of 4.0 m impacting different cliffs: (a)Undamaged cliff, (b) Submerged cliff, and (c) Partially submerged cliff. For each panel row, the distance scale is uniform in both spatial directions.

inside the notch and a returning flow moving above it along the cliff face. This pattern continues until the recession is complete. However, in contrast to the submerged case, two vortices form inside the notch: a lower vortex that circulates outward with negative velocity, and an upper vortex, located just beneath the notch’s top wall, that circulates inward with positive velocity.

In terms of velocity magnitude, horizontal velocity is not remarkably affected by the cliff geometry, remaining between approximately -3.5 m/s and $+2.7$ with a minimal variation across the different cases.

Compared to the submerged case, the partially submerged geometry

allows more energetic horizontal entry and retains flow motion shorter due to reduced blockage. While the undamaged cliff reflects energy directly, the notched geometry absorbs and store part of the horizontal momentum, altering base-level circulation and potentially influencing erosion.

Increasing the wave height to 4 m, the horizontal flow dynamics at the cliff base become significantly more energetic and complex, as shown in Fig. 15. In the undamaged case, the incoming flow at 17 s exhibits moderate horizontal velocity (5.5 m/s) near the cliff base. However, at the peak of run-up (18.7 s), there is a conflict between the

Fig. 14. Horizontal velocity field for a wave height of 2.0 m impacting different cliffs: (a)Undamaged cliff, (b) Submerged cliff, and (c) Partially submerged cliff. For each panel row, the distance scale is uniform in both spatial directions.

incoming flow and returning flow.

On this interface some water particles will be pushed toward the free surface and the rest toward the seabed, but it finishes in tranquility. For the submerged cliff, the same phenomena are observed, and also the water stream along the cliff face contains two vortices. In addition, a vortex forms inside the notch after the water reaches the top and begins to recede, and the vortex remaining within the notch even after the run-down phase. In the partially submerged case, a large circulation pattern with a velocity of approximately 2 m/s persists as the wave impacts and rises to its highest point, indicating a more organized run-up process. However, once the run down begins, a vortex forms inside the notch

with a velocity of around 2 m/s, which is higher than in the other cliff types.

The comparative analysis of velocity fields across the three cliff geometries reveals that the presence and configuration of a notch play a crucial role in shaping both vertical and horizontal flow behavior during solitary wave interaction. While the undamaged cliff reflects the incoming wave energy more directly, resulting in sharp but short-lived run-up and rundown events, the submerged and partially submerged notches induce more complex internal circulation patterns. These notches disrupt the uniformity of wave motion, redistribute momentum, and give rise to persistent vortices that affect both the magnitude and

Fig. 15. Horizontal velocity field for a wave height of 4.0 m impacting different cliffs: (a)Undamaged cliff, (b) Submerged cliff, and (c) Partially submerged cliff. For each panel row, the distance scale is uniform in both spatial directions.

duration of flow near the cliff base. Particularly under larger wave conditions, the partially submerged notch generates the most energetic vertical jets, while also sustaining elevated internal velocities during recession. Overall, the notch geometry governs not only the spatial distribution of flow but also its intensity and timing, highlighting its critical role in modulating wave energy dissipation and near-cliff hydrodynamics.

5.2. Wave runup

Fig. 16 displays the wave propagation procedure for the smallest and largest wave height, 0.5 m and 4.0 m respectively. Fig. 16a represents the 0.5 m wave condition and shows a gradual and smooth increase in water level at each wave gauge, culminating in the highest run-up level on the cliff. This behavior results from early wave reflection, as solitary wave theory indicates that smaller wave heights correspond to longer

Fig. 16. Wave propagation procedure for (a) 0.5 wave height and (b) 4 m wave height.

wavelength. Obviously, the cliff shape doesn't make any difference in the wave propagation and run-up shape as the water surface cannot touch the cliff surface in the 0.5 m wave height. Generally, this indicates that the spatial scale of the wave governs the interaction length with the cliff face.

On the other hand, a rapid and sudden rise of the water level on the cliff is evident for the 4.0 m wave height case. According to Fig. 16b, none of the wave gauges positioned before the cliff show any indication of the cliff's presence, as the wavelength is short enough to not disturb the incoming waves. However, the presence of the cliff influences both the magnitude and progression of the run-up, particularly when the incoming wave volume collides with the cliff protrusion, as observed in the partially submerged notched cliff. The actual wet surface begins at 2.0 m, where an indentation appears along the run-up line. Below this level, water fills the cavity, leading to localized trapping that reduces the wave's upwards momentum and consequently influences both timing and extent of the cliff's wet surface.

Fig. 17 shows a comparison of run-up time history between all cases under different wave conditions. Although there is no significant distinction up to a wave height of 1.0 m, from 1.5 m onwards there is a change in both the run-up height and its trend. In general, the presence

of a notch reduces the run-up, with the effect becoming more pronounced under larger wave conditions. As expected, the run-up pattern changes as the wave first becomes trapped in the notch, then strikes the external corner, and finally begins to ascend the cliff face.

This behavior emphasizes the role of wave energy partitioning: while the notch dissipates or redirects part of the energy, the cliff face above still receives the remaining upward motion when wave amplitude is sufficient to overtop the notch.

Fig. 18 shows how the maximum runup increases with wave height for the three different cliff geometries. Consistent with Fig. 17, as the waves get larger, the difference becomes more pronounced up to the highest wave conditions where the maximum run-up is 10 and 30 percent less than the undamaged cliff in the submerged and partially submerged cases, respectively.

The nonlinear increase of the wave runup can be captured by second order polynomials that are a function of the wave height and the cliff geometry (see the legend of Fig. 17).

However, the maximum run-up height is not the only factor determining the severity of the situation. As already discussed in the literature, it is important to identify how long the water remains on the cliff and find the opportunity to penetrate cracks and fractures. This

Fig. 17. Run-up time history of different cases under various wave heights (H).

mechanism applies pressure and force to the cliff from inside and contributes to the degradation of the material. Fig. 17 also reveals how long it takes for water to move up and down the cliff in all cases and scenarios. It reveals that a notched cliff tends to hold water on its surface for a longer period, especially when the notch is submerged. This prolonged retention is critical because repeated wetting and drying cycles under wave can accelerate weathering. Furthermore, if waves are frequent, this delay in drainage implies partial saturation between events, sustaining elevated pore pressure within the cliff mass.

Fig. 19 therefore shows the “Exposure Time” which is the time that the cliff is wet in a wave cycle. This indicates that a submerged notch significantly alters the exposure condition of the cliff, potentially increasing its vulnerability to water-related erosion, and this effect should be accounted in future vulnerability assessments. Unlike the maximum runup, which follows similar trends for all cases, the behavior of the exposure time of a cliff with a submerged notch varies with the wave height. As shown in this figure, exposure time tends to decrease with increasing wave height, but there is a turning point in the

submerged notch case at which exposure time begins to increase again.

This non-monotonic behavior suggests that beyond a certain wave energy level, secondary processes such as backwash interface, vortex formation, or cavity circulation begin to dominate, altering the interaction dynamics and delaying water recession. Nevertheless, the exposure time difference between submerged notch case and the undamaged cliff rises by increasing the wave height.

For instance, the exposure time for the submerged notch is about 17 s under a 4 m wave which is 70 percent higher than an undamaged cliff. For the partially submerged cliff, the period of the cliff wet surface reduces significantly to slightly over 2 s for the same wave and it is null for waves below 2.5 m as the whole water traps inside the cavity.

As mentioned above, when the cliff height is large enough that even the highest wave cannot overtop, the exposure time becomes more critical since it measures a quantity that indicates how much water has been given the opportunity to penetrate. Therefore, another parameter (Contact Exposure), shown in Fig. 20, is defined to evaluate the exposure time in combination with the wetted surface of the cliff. This parameter,

Fig. 18. Maximum run-up correlation across all wave heights for each cliff type.

Fig. 19. Time exposure of all cliff types under different wave conditions for each cliff type.

Fig. 20. Volume exposure of all cliff types under different wave conditions.

which is the area between the run-up time history and still water level (for the partially submerged, the cliff's wet surface starts from above the notch), indicates how much water has had time to impact on the cliff for how long. This integrated metric offers a more comprehensive measure of cliff vulnerability as it combines the intensity and duration of

hydrodynamic interactions. The Contact exposure diagram also shows that a submerged notched cliff is exposed to about 60 % more water than an intact one. To put this into perspective, while a 4-meter wave is hitting a cliff, the former is exposed to 55 m of water in 1 s, while the latter is exposed to 35 m of water per second.

5.3. Flow velocity

While the run-up height and exposure quantify the extent and duration of water presence on the cliff, they do not reveal how the flow evolves once the wave climbs the surface. In other words, based on run-up metrics, it seems a cliff with a notch is naturally preserved, but the temporal and vertical distribution of flow velocity shows how velocity spreads, concentrates, or recirculates during water motion along the cliff surface and inside the cavity, which can vary significantly depending on wave height and cliff geometry and activate different modes of vulnerability. To deepen our understanding of these processes, the following section examines the spatial and temporal patterns of flow velocity around the cliff under various wave and geometric conditions.

5.4. Time varying velocity profile on the cliff surface

It is expected that increasing the wave height ascends the water motion velocity on the cliff, but looking at Fig. 21, the presence of the notch also increases the range of the tangential vertical velocity of water on the cliff. On the undamaged cliff, under all wave conditions, the vertical velocity follows a nearly consistent trend. As time progresses, it increases smoothly until the water reaches a certain elevation on the cliff. At that point, a turning point occurs, and despite the elevation continuing to rise, the velocity starts to decrease until it reaches zero at the maximum run-up height. Then, during the rundown, the velocity becomes negative. The water first runs down slowly and then accelerates as it nears the base of the cliff. Interestingly, the velocity magnitude changes almost linearly with elevation, both during ascent and descent, except in the 4.0 m wave height, where an abrupt change in velocity appears during the rundown phase.

This regular and symmetric behavior of vertical velocity in the undamaged cliff implies a stable and predictable flow regime, where energy is gradually dissipated both during ascent and descent. Such a pattern reflects a lower likelihood of localized concentration of velocity that could induce structural damage or erosion. The deviation observed in the highest wave condition may signal the onset of nonlinearity and flow separation during rundown, which can affect the way water re-contacts the lower cliff and base.

In the submerged cliff, the overall vertical velocity range is larger than that of the undamaged cliff and the profile becomes asymmetric between run-up and run-down. This is most evident at 4.0 m wave height, where the maximum velocity during run-up reaches about 7.5 m/s, while the maximum run-down velocity is only about 3m/s. The position of the peak velocity also shifts along the cliff depending on wave height. In this case, the velocity profile is highly nonlinear in both phases. For example, while one point may show a very high velocity, neighboring points at nearly the same elevation may show almost zero velocity. This fragmented structure suggests uneven momentum transfer along the cliff face, which may lead to localized stress concentrations or zones of repeated wetting and drying. The reduction in rundown velocity implies that water may remain on parts of the cliff longer, enhancing exposure and potentially increasing its vulnerability to infiltration and long-term degradation. The spatial incoherence in velocity also hints at turbulence or chaotic flow near the transition from submerged zone to exposed cliff face, where wave reflection and confinement may play a role.

The third cliff case shows a particularly interesting behavior at 2 m wave height. Contrary to expectations, a lower wave height does not correspond to lower velocities anymore. Here, the water depth is 4 m and cliff starts at $z = 6$ m, meaning the water surface becomes tangent to

Fig. 21. Time-evolving vertical profiles of the vertical component of flow velocity in front of the cliff face for three wave heights: (a) 2.0 m, (b) 3.0 m, and (c) 4.0 m.

the notch top. In higher waves cases like 3 m and 4 m, this jet does not appear while having significant velocity magnitude. So, the 2 m wave case results in an unexpectedly high vertical velocity.

In other wave heights, while no similar jet is observed, the velocity profile still shows heavy disturbance, with large variations in velocity between neighboring elevations.

This demonstrates that certain combinations of wave height and geometry can result in resonance-like effects or flow focusing, where moderate waves align with structural features to generate unexpectedly

high velocities. In fact, the resonance-like jet in the 2.0 m case results from the internal circulation inside the notch colliding with the incoming wave, which amplifies the flow and redirects it toward the cliff. In larger waves, however, the wave front strikes the wall directly, so, the impact intensity stems only from the incoming wave energy, and no such amplification develops.

Such jets can pose a risk of impact damage, material detachment, or internal pressurization in narrow cavities. The irregularity and inconsistency in the vertical velocity field also suggest unsteady flow paths

Fig. 22. Time-evolving vertical profiles of the horizontal component of flow velocity in front of the cliff face for three wave heights: (a) 2.0 m, (b) 3.0 m, and (c) 4.0 m.

that could favor erosion along specific weak zones in the cliff material.

In general, more symmetry is observed in the partially submerged case than submerged. This may be attributed to the delayed contact between the wave and the vertical cliff face, allowing the wave front to reorganize before reaching the exposed surface. The smoother transition from horizontal to vertical flow reduces asymmetry, though localized disturbances still occur.

Now, it is clarified that the cliff configuration significantly affects

vertical flow dynamics, with velocities in some cases exceeding those in the undamaged cliff by more than a factor of 20. Such a dramatic increase underscores the importance of geometry in modulating not just run-up height but also the internal energy distribution of the wave. High vertical velocities can enhance water penetration into rock discontinuities and increase the mechanical stress on near-surface layers and may accelerate cliff weakening even in the absence of overtopping.

It is generally expected that the horizontal component of velocity

Fig. 23. Vertical profile of vertical velocity for wave height $H = 1.5\text{m}$: (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially submerged Notch. The labels above each panel indicate the time t at which the velocity profile is extracted.

near a vertical cliff is smaller than the vertical one, particularly during the run-up phase when motion is mostly upward. However, Fig. 22 clearly shows that horizontal velocities exhibit complex behavior, especially in the notched configurations, and can reach significant magnitudes depending on wave height and the location along the cliff.

In the undamaged cliff, the horizontal velocity remains minimal across all wave heights. For the 2 m wave height, values remain within almost ± 0.004 m/s, with very smooth and steady profiles over time. As wave height increases to 3 m, the peak velocity remains around ± 0.01 m/s and continues to follow a consistent, symmetric pattern both spatially and temporally. In the highest wave case, the velocity magnitude slightly increases but not more than ~ 0.03 m/s. Overall, these profiles confirm that in the absence of geometric disturbance, the horizontal velocity of flow remains negligible, stable, and symmetric throughout interaction. This behavior suggests a highly streamlined, vertically dominant flow with little lateral deviation or swirl. Such low and consistent horizontal velocity indicates reduced risk of shear erosion or sideward flow penetration, contributing to the long-term stability of the cliff surface.

In the submerged cliff, however, the behavior changes dramatically. At 2 m wave height, horizontal velocity reaches values of nearly 1.0 m/s, with asymmetry and oscillations concentrated around the notch level. As time progresses, the flow near the cliff shows rapid changes in direction, and the velocity becomes highly non-uniform along the vertical axis. These alternating layers correspond to unsteady flow behavior, possibly due to localized flow detachment, wave reflection, or vortex shedding around the geometry transition. In the 4 m wave case, this unsteadiness becomes extreme. Horizontal velocity values exceed 2 m/s, and the profiles reveal sharp gradients and reveals in narrow elevation ranges.

In the partially submerged cliff, the behavior becomes even more dramatic. For the 2 m wave, a horizontal velocity burst appears around $z = 6$ m, reaching values over 6 m/s. This strong lateral jet occurs abruptly and fades away as time progresses. In 3 m wave, a similar horizontal spike reaches around 5 m/s and is tightly confined in time and elevation. At the highest wave condition, the jet intensifies further, reaching horizontal velocities about 15 m/s near the cliff level. These horizontal jets result from strong flow deflection. When the wave front aligns with the base of the cliff, a portion of the wave momentum is redirected sideways, forming short-lived but intense lateral ejections. The concentrated nature of these jets implies a risk of severe horizontal shear and erosion at the contact zone.

Moreover, in both submerged and partially submerged cases, the horizontal velocity profile lacks the smooth symmetry seen in the undamaged cliff. Instead, it exhibits disorganized structures, sharp transitions, and direct reversals that suggest chaotic or unsteady flow dynamics. Such irregular horizontal motion is likely to create concentrated zones of erosion or wetting along the cliff, particularly where velocity gradients are steep. This unpredictable behavior becomes more severe with increasing wave energy and may affect the structural integrity of the cliff over time.

Comparing all three cliff types confirms geometry has a profound effect on the horizontal velocity field, especially at notch-cliff contact zones. While the undamaged cliff maintains horizontal velocities on the order of 0.006 m/s, the partially submerged cliff under 2 m waves exceeds 6 m/s, an increase of more than 1000 times (in 2.0 m wave height). This striking difference highlights that, even in the absence of overtopping or high run-up, internal flow dynamics, especially horizontal, can be responsible for intense, localized instability. Such effects may be overlooked if only vertical motion is considered.

Fig. 24. Vertical profile of vertical velocity for wave height $H = 3.5\text{m}$: (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially submerged Notch. The labels above each panel indicate the time t at which the velocity profile is extracted.

5.5. Velocity circulation inside the notch

Apart from flow patterns in front of the cliff, there is a very important flow circulation inside the notch of the damaged cliffs.

Fig. 23 shows the vertical profile of vertical component of velocity at six stations, distributed along the notch depth from entrance (station at $x = 0.25\text{ m}$) to the back wall ($x = 1.5\text{ m}$), under a 1.5 m wave height. Each profile represents how vertical velocity varies with elevation along a vertical line at the station. The top row corresponds to the submerged cliff configuration, and the bottom row to the partially submerged cliff. The three columns represent early entry, peak runup, and end of rundown on the cliff.

In the submerged case, during the early entry stage, vertical velocities are weak and mostly upward, concentrating near the notch top, except for the last stations, that shows a negative velocity that implies a circulation downward. It suggests the existence of a vortex-like flow trapping at the top internal corner of the notch. At peak run-up, vertical motion becomes more pronounced across all stations, with stringer upward velocity this time, meaning the water is pushing from below. However, the profiles are not symmetrical, and a clear imbalance remains between the front and back stations. At the end of running down, the vertical velocity varies sharply between stations. The flow has reversed in most locations, but the magnitude and shape differ significantly. In this stage the highest turbulence happens when the velocity is much higher, about 20 times, and its profile is positive in some parts and negative at the rest. This recirculating pattern increases the water residence time and may contribute to localized erosion, especially near the rear wall and upper regions of the notch.

In the partially submerged case, the flow is more organized. Already at the entry stage, all stations show moderate upward velocity, increasing gradually with elevation. At peak run-up, the profiles become smooth and consistently shaped, with velocity increasing toward the front of the notch. The flow appears synchronized across all stations. At the end of rundown, all curves clearly reverse direction, forming a strong and coherent downward motion, with nearly parallel profiles across the notch. This behavior is more a piston-like mechanism. Where the notch fills and drains in a single, directed motion without signs of recirculation or delay.

Fig. 24 explains what happens if the wave crest intersects directly with the notch external corner as the wave height is 3.5 m . In the submerged cliff, the entry shows upward velocity across all stations, decreasing gradually toward the rear. This reflects an initial rising motion of water inside the notch, initiated from the wave impact at the opening.

At peak run-up, the front station develops a clear downward velocity at higher elevations. This sharp contrast indicates that the wave crest strikes the top external corner of the notch and redirects flow vertically downward, forming a localized small jet. By the 30 s , the water surface is still higher than the initial level and at the same vertical level, there are both negative and positive velocities that show a persistent vortex inside the notch when the flow is not receded completely. Thus, in this case, the flow circulation is in act for a very longer time than usual, increasing the risk of erosion and infiltration.

For the partially submerged cliff, the flow is smoother and more coordinated. At entry, all stations show similar upward velocities. During maximum run-up, the profiles indicate strong upward flow,

Fig. 25. Vertical profile of horizontal velocity for wave height $H = 1.5\text{m}$: (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially submerged Notch. The labels above each panel indicate the time t at which the velocity profile is extracted.

increasing toward the entry of the notch. At 25.5 s, run down completes, when all stations show downward velocity, without any circulation. So, the intersection of a high wave crest with the notch free corner leads to vertical redirection, early asymmetry, and flow instability in the submerged case, while the partially submerged case preserves a more organized filling and drainage process.

Fig. 25 shows the horizontal component of velocity for 1.5 m wave at the same stations and times. In the submerged notch the horizontal velocity remains low and mostly uniform in the early stage, with small positive values near the top except the last station. As the wave progresses to peak run-up, the horizontal velocity is negligible at most of the notch back wall height, but a circulating pattern is obvious at the top. In the end of the runup procedure, velocity range is much higher, around 10 times, that reveals when the cliff exposure to water finishes, the water circulation inside the notch starts to impose a risk on the cliff at the base. Flow here is also very turbulent and circulating.

In the partially submerged case (Fig. 25b) the velocity of the water is concentrated at the top in the beginning of the run-up procedure, which is much more than in the submerged notch. At the peak run-up, there is a clear returning flow that moves toward the notch back wall in lower levels and toward the sea from higher elevations. This is more pronounced in the first station. In contrast to the submerged cliff, the maximum velocity inside the notch happens at this time, when the whole height of the notch is filled with water. After the recession, the flow reverses relative to the early stage, with negative velocity at lower levels and positive at the top. This pattern emphasizes the increased potential for water circulation within the submerged notch, whereas the partially submerged case experiences the highest velocity as a jet flowing tangentially along its upper boundary.

Fig. 26a indicates there is no turbulence at the run-up initiation phase when a 3.5 m wave is hitting the submerged notch. Rather, it is just an inflow from below and an outflow from upper levels. At the max run-up stage, it becomes the opposite, meaning there is an inflow from upper levels and outflow from lower levels that behave like jets especially at the upper notch boundary, since the flow velocity is almost zero in the height and suddenly reaches 0.1 m/s near the top. In this case, the water is trapped inside the notch and barely gets back to the initial water level while the water keeps circulating and making turbulence with a velocity of around 1 m/s, 10 times higher than the maximum velocity in the previous stage. It shows how vulnerable this configuration is to water circulation inside the notch as it has a big velocity magnitude and the duration is very long.

In the partially submerged case, there is a consistent velocity profile across all stations, but the velocity reduces in closer stations to the notch back wall. This time, the velocity is completely positive, which is expected as the water is trying to fill the notch and still goes forward. The circulation happens at the peak run-up moment. At this instance, the notch is filled with water, and we see an inflow from bottom and outflow from the top. Compared to submerged case, the max run-up happens when maximum velocity is also happening, which is smaller than the maximum velocity in submerged case. In the end of run-up, the water is mainly going out of the notch while there is a turbulence at the water surface.

5.6. Water velocity pattern next to the notch internal surface

The next two figures focus on the ability of water to affect the notch internal surfaces. Fig. 27 shows horizontal velocity distribution close to

Fig. 26. Vertical profile of horizontal velocity for wave height $H = 3.5\text{m}$: (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially submerged Notch. The labels above each panel indicate the time t at which the velocity profile is extracted.

the notch back wall during the run-up procedure time. In both cliff types, elevated horizontal velocities persist adjacent to the back wall, particularly during mid-to-late stages of run-up. For the submerged notch, the velocity magnitude increases with wave height, peaking at over 0.3 m/s in the 3.0 m , not 4.0 m wave.

This fact indicates there is a nonlinear phenomenon. The profiles also show sharp reversals and localized accelerations near the notch top wall, suggesting recirculating eddies. In the partially submerged notch cliff, the velocity magnitude becomes more oscillatory in time and space, reaching nearly 0.8 m/s in the 4.0 m case. The pronounced and persistent high-speed streaks directed toward and along the rear wall may represent significant tangential loading, implying a high potential for shear-induced erosion or mechanical scouring of the surface over repeated wave events. These patterns suggest that the rear wall of the notch, although not directly impacted by the initial wave front, remains vulnerable to sustained horizontal flow intrusion.

In both types, the velocity range is very similar in 3.0 m and 4.0 m waves and keeps the danger high even with smaller waves.

Fig. 28 shows the horizontal distribution of vertical velocity along the notch top surface. In the submerged cliff, for all wave heights, there is a consistent positive flow velocity until the near peak run-up stages with a restricted velocity that gradually rises with the wave height increment. But after the peak happens, the velocity profile shows more variations.

After the peak runup height under 2.0 m wave, almost half of the notch depth from the entry has negative velocity while after that, the vertical velocity of water is positive, tending to go inside the cliff. at 3.0 m , there is a significant negative velocity increase after run-up at the entrance about 0.4 m/s but doesn't affect the positive velocity at the internal corner so much. The most interesting case happens in 4.0 m

wave, where about the one-third-of the notch depth both from the internal and the external corner toward the center have positive velocity, with maximum velocity 0.3 m/s , and at the same time, around the middle of the notch depth, there is negative velocity around 0.6 m/s . In contrast, the partially submerged cliff shows a much more stable and horizontally stratified velocity structure.

The flow remains primarily upward, and the magnitude remains moderate across all wave heights. Even though after the run-up peaks, the water is not in contact to the notch top in most of the time, it creates higher negative velocity while being in contact, which is around 0.8 m/s in all wave heights.

The results can be directly connected to engineering frameworks used for assessing cliff stability and erosion susceptibility. Engineering indices such as the Cliff Stability Index (CSI) [47] use hydraulic and geomorphological factors to assess susceptibility, where the Wave Energy Index is computed from the run-up magnitude and represents the impact at the cliff base. However, present results show that cliff geometry can change the run-up pattern, reduce run-up height but increase flow retention and localized impact intensity, including unexpected jetting. Therefore, runup alone could be misleading in some cases, and future indices should also include geometry-dependent effects flow patterns. According to Zhao et al. [48], wave action under typhoon conditions causes abrasive forces resulting in the formation of a notch at the cliff base, which initiates the instability and leads to toppling combined with the effects of rainfall-induced weakening. Based on the present study, findings show that the presence of a notch is not only a geometric void beneath an overhanging block, but also a driver of new hydrodynamic behavior. It is demonstrated that the notch alters wave motion by increasing flow retention, producing localized jets, and causing highly variable impact patterns that could accelerate erosion

Fig. 27. Vertical distribution of horizontal velocity adjacent to the notch back wall under various wave heights (H): (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially Submerged Notch.

around the notch and promote seawater infiltration into cracks, thereby enlarging the notch and weakening the rock mass. The present study focused on cliffs that can be modeled in 2D due to their uniform shape along the coastline. However, this is not always the case in nature. Cliffs may have features that generate 3D processes, such as a finite notch length that alters turbulence around the impact zone and consequently affects the velocity field or runup mechanism. To address this gap, future research should combine a broad 2D parametric study with a set of representative 3D simulations to identify how these features modify the hydrodynamics. Once this relationship is established, machine learning can be used to transfer the 3D corrections back into 2D modeling, allowing runup, velocity, and exposure time to be estimated efficiently while accounting for key 3D effects. It is noteworthy that recently machine learning reduced-order models have been used to achieve real-time field prediction [49] and to predict future time steps of the simulations while avoiding the need to iteratively solve the expensive Navier–Stokes equations [50]. Similar ROM approaches have also reproduced hydrodynamic behavior and erosion wear inside a pipe in agreement with CFD results while reducing computational time [51]. Furthermore, surrogate modeling approaches have been used to support engineering reliability analysis and structural response prediction, where data-driven models take offshore environmental or mechanical loading as input and produce fast estimates of failure probability or fatigue performance [52]. This suggests that such modeling approaches can be extended to cliff environments. The hydrodynamic results obtained here provide high-fidelity inputs required for future ROM or ML frameworks that aim to not only reconstruct flow fields but also predict their erosive consequences on coastal cliffs.

6. Conclusions

This study performed a high-fidelity CFD investigation to quantify and compare the hydrodynamic interactions of solitary waves with three different cliff geometries including an undamaged vertical cliff, a damaged cliff with a submerged notch, and a damaged cliff with a partially submerged notch that are representative of natural morphologies observed along a sea cliff in the coastline of the Ventotene island (Italy). Through 24 simulations across a spectrum of wave heights up to 4.0 m, the research demonstrated that cliff geometry critically governs the distribution of wave energy, the extent of run-up, and the internal flow behavior, each contributing to the vulnerability of the cliff.

The results show that while an undamaged sea cliff experiences the highest run-up height, it reflects wave energy directly, resulting in shorter contact durations and more streamlined, vertically dominant flow. This makes it most susceptible to overtopping and direct impact, especially when high wave crests rapidly convert their kinematic energy into vertical motion near the cliff face. In contrast, a submerged notch cliff reduces the maximum run-up by up to 10 % but prolongs the exposure time by approximately 70 %, allowing for persistent turbulent circulation and increased water residence inside the notch scar and on the sea cliff surface. The velocity inside the notch increases significantly during the rundown phase, in some cases reaching values up to twenty times higher than those during run-up. These conditions could facilitate sea water upward injection into cracks and fractures, especially under high-frequency wave events thus increasing the potential for internal weakening.

Meanwhile, the partially submerged cliff introduces a hybrid

Fig. 28. Horizontal distribution of vertical velocity adjacent to the notch top wall under various wave heights (H): (a) Submerged Notch and (b) Partially Submerged Notch.

mechanism. Although it shows the greatest reduction in run-up height among all geometries (up to 30 %), it experiences intense vertical and horizontal jets, especially when the wave crest aligns with the notch top wall. Notably, smaller waves such as the 2.0 m case produce more focused water jets than larger ones, suggesting a resonance-like effect that enhances localized impact. This configuration is highly prone to impact-induced damage and shear-driven wear, in particular when flow focusing amplifies jet formation and extends the duration of energetic horizontal motion.

To provide a clearer understanding of the velocity distribution along the cliff face, the results show that horizontal velocity on the exposed cliff surface is approximately zero. However, within the notch, the horizontal velocity ranges between 0.1 and 1 m/s, depending on the incident wave height and geometric characteristics of the notch.

The synthesis of run-up metrics, flow field evolution, and velocity profile analysis confirms that each cliff configuration faces distinct hydrodynamic effects and threats. The undamaged cliff is primarily exposed to short-duration, high-energy impact; the submerged notch to prolonged wetting and internal vortex circulation, and the partially submerged geometry to concentrated jets and increased risk of infiltration. These important conclusions were reached based on validated 2D CFD models, which are expected to represent realistically the wave-cliff interaction under a normal wave impact on cliffs (i.e. 90° wave propagation angle relative to the spanwise direction of cliff) that have constant geometrical properties in the spanwise direction. However, future studies should develop three-dimensional models especially for cases with an oblique wave impact or cliffs with a changing geometry in the

spanwise direction, in order to evaluate the applicability of the current findings to more complex conditions that can be found in nature.

As a main final remark, this research highlights the importance of accounting for natural morphological features such as basal notches when assessing wave-driven hazards to sea cliffs. The findings underscore that geomorphological state strongly modulates the spatial and temporal characteristics of wave-induced exposure and that vulnerability should not be inferred from run-up height alone. A comprehensive risk assessment must integrate exposure time, internal flow structures and dynamic velocity profiles to fully capture the erosion and failure potential under extreme marine conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Raouf Sobhani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Federico Feliziani:** Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Gian Marco Marmoni:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Salvatore Martino:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Denis Istrati:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] L. Mentaschi, M.I. Voudoukas, E. Voukouvalas, A. Dosio, L. Feyen, Global changes of extreme coastal wave energy fluxes triggered by intensified teleconnection patterns, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 44 (5) (2017) 2416–2426, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL072488>.
- [2] I.R. Young, A. Ribal, Multiplatform evaluation of global trends in wind speed and wave height, *Science* (1979) 364 (6440) (2019) 548–552, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aav9527>.
- [3] B.G. Reguero, L.J. Losada, F.J. Méndez, A recent increase in global wave power as a consequence of oceanic warming, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (1) (2019) 205, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-08066-0>.
- [4] H. Lobeto, A. Semedo, G. Lemos, A. Dastgheib, M. Menendez, R. Ranasinghe, J.-R. Bidlot, Global coastal wave storminess, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1) (2024) 3726, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-51420-0>.
- [5] C. Ioannidis, S. Verykokou, S. Soile, D. Istrati, C. Spyarakos, A. Sarris, D. Akritidis, H. Feidas, A.K. Georgoulas, E. Tringa, P. Zanis, C. Georgiadis, S. Martino, F. Feliziani, G.M. Marmoni, D. Cerra, M. Ottinger, F. Bachofer, A. Anastasiou, G. C. Anyfantis, Safeguarding our heritage—The TRIQUETRA project approach, *Heritage* 7 (2) (2024) 758–793, <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7020037>.
- [6] T. Sunamura, A relationship between wave-induced cliff erosion and erosive force of waves, *J. Geol.* 85 (5) (1977) 613–618, <https://doi.org/10.1086/628340>.
- [7] A.H. Sallenger, W. Krabill, J. Brock, R. Swift, S. Manizade, H. Stockdon, Sea-cliff erosion as a function of beach changes and extreme wave runup during the 1997–1998 El Niño, *Mar. Geol.* 187 (3–4) (2002) 279–297, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(02\)00316-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(02)00316-X).
- [8] M.L. Palmsten, R.A. Holman, Laboratory investigation of dune erosion using stereo video, *Coast. Eng.* 60 (2012) 123–135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2011.09.003>.
- [9] J.D. Hansom, N.D.P. Bartrop, A.M. Hall, Modelling the processes of cliff-top erosion and deposition under extreme storm waves, *Mar. Geol.* 253 (1–2) (2008) 36–50, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2008.02.015>.
- [10] Y. Shen, C.N. Whittaker, M.E. Dickson, Cliff notching due to swash abrasion: insights from physical experiments, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 51 (19) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL112175> e2024GL112175.
- [11] P. Alessio, E.A. Keller, Short-term patterns and processes of coastal cliff erosion in Santa Barbara, California, *Geomorphology* 353 (2020) 106994, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2019.106994>.
- [12] R.J. Bergillos, C. Rodriguez-Delgado, L. Medina, G. Iglesias, Coastal cliff exposure and management, *Ocean. Coast. Manag.* 198 (2020) 105387, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105387>.
- [13] A.P. Young, R.T. Guza, H. Matsumoto, M.A. Merrifield, W.C. O’Reilly, Z.M. Swirad, Three years of weekly observations of coastal cliff erosion by waves and rainfall, *Geomorphology* 375 (2021) 107545, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2020.107545>.
- [14] C. Earlie, G. Masselink, P. Russell, The role of beach morphology on coastal cliff erosion under extreme waves, *Earth. Surf. Process. Landf.* 43 (6) (2018) 1213–1228, <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4308>.
- [15] N.W.H. Allsop, J.E. McKenna, D. Vicinanza, T.T.J. Whittaker, New design methods for wave impact loadings on vertical breakwaters and seawalls, *Coast. Eng.* 1996 (1997) 2508–2521, <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784402429.194>.
- [16] G. Cuomo, W. Allsop, T. Bruce, J. Pearson, Breaking wave loads at vertical seawalls and breakwaters, *Coast. Eng.* 57 (4) (2010) 424–439, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2009.11.005>.
- [17] M. Tirindelli, G. Cuomo, W. Allsop, K. McConnell, Exposed jetties: inconsistencies and gaps in design methods for wave-induced forces, *Coast. Eng. 2002: Solving Coast. Conundrums* (2003) 1684–1696.
- [18] T. Xiang, D. Istrati, Assessment of extreme wave impact on coastal decks with different geometries via the arbitrary lagrangian-eulerian method, *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 9 (12) (2021) 1342, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9121342>.
- [19] A. Hasanpour, D. Istrati, “Extreme storm wave impact on elevated coastal buildings,” in *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Nat. Hazards Infrastruct.* (ICONHC 2022), Athens, Greece, 2022, pp. 5–7, ISSN 2623-4513, EID: 2-s2.0-85138338688.
- [20] M. Heidarzadeh, M. Sheibani, R.J. Luis-Fonseca, F. Nowak, Runup of solitary waves on high strength steel mesh rock mattress revetments: experiments and empirical equations, *Results. Eng.* 27 (2025) 105899, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105899>.
- [21] H. Moss, M. Heidarzadeh, R. Sabeti, Innovative coastal defence using rock bag revetments: preliminary physical modelling, *Results. Eng.* (2025) 105151, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105151>.
- [22] H. Matsumoto, M.E. Dickson, W.J. Stephenson, C.F. Thompson, A.P. Young, Modeling future cliff-front waves during sea level rise and implications for coastal cliff retreat rates, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1) (2024) 7810, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-57923-0>.
- [23] Y. Shen, C.N. Whittaker, C.F. Thompson, A.C. Raby, A.P. Young, M.E. Dickson, Wave impacts on vertical cliffs: insights from laboratory experiments and field observations, *Coast. Eng.* 201 (2025) 104794, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2025.104794>.
- [24] Í. Aniel-Quiroga, C. Vidal, J.L. Lara, M. González, Pressures on a rubble-mound breakwater crown-wall for tsunami impact, *Coast. Eng.* 152 (2019) 103522, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2019.103522>.
- [25] D. Istrati, I. Buckle, P. Lomonaco, S. Yim, Deciphering the tsunami wave impact and associated connection forces in open-girder coastal bridges, *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 6 (4) (2018) 148, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse6040148>.
- [26] B.R. Seiffert, R. Cengiz Ertekin, I.N. Robertson, Effect of entrapped air on solitary wave forces on a coastal bridge deck with girders, *J. Bridge Eng.* 21 (2) (2016) 04015036, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0000799](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0000799).
- [27] S. Tadeipalli, C.E. Synolakis, The run-up of N-waves on sloping beaches, *Proc. R. Soc. London. Ser. A: Math. Phys. Sci.* 445 (1994) 99–112, 1923.
- [28] P.A. Madsen, D.R. Fuhrman, H.A. Schäffer, On the solitary wave paradigm for tsunamis, *J. Geophys. Res.: Oceans* 113 (2008). C12.
- [29] D. Ruberti, E. Marino, A. Pignalosa, P. Romano, M. Vigliotti, Assessment of tuff sea cliff stability integrating geological surveys and remote sensing: case history from Ventotene Island (Southern Italy), *Remote Sens. (Basel)* 12 (12) (2020) 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12122006>.
- [30] F. Feliziani, G.M. Marmoni, V. Gianni, A.F. Fernandes, A. Pegurri, G. Grechi, G. Felli, P. Ciampi, F. Bozzano, C. Delpino, C. Arrighi, S. Martino, Engineering-geological modelling as a tool for archaeological site preservation strategies, *Italian J. Eng. Geol. Environ.*, 1(2024.1S) (2024) 115, <https://doi.org/10.4408/IJEGE.2024-01.S-13>.
- [31] T. Sunamura, *Geomorphology of Rocky Coasts*, John Wiley & Sons, 1992.
- [32] W. Schwanghart, D. Scherler, TopoToolbox 2—MATLAB-based software for topographic analysis and modeling in Earth surface sciences, *Earth Surf. Dyn.* 2 (1) (2014) 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.5194/esurf-2-1-2014>.
- [33] Sobhani, R., Istrati, D., Martino, S., Marmoni, G.M., & Feliziani, F. (2025, March 18). CFD investigation of wave runup on coastal cliffs for impact assessment on cultural heritage. EGU General Assembly 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusph-ere-egu25-19751>.
- [34] R. Sabeti, M. Heidarzadeh, A. Romano, G. Barajas Ojeda, J.L. Lara, Three-dimensional simulations of subaerial landslide-generated waves: comparing openfoam and flow-3d hydro models, *Pure Appl. Geophys.* 181 (4) (2024) 1075–1093, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00024-024-03443-x>.
- [35] B.E. Larsen, D.R. Fuhrman, J. Roenby, Performance of interFoam on the simulation of progressive waves, *Coast. Eng. J.* 61 (3) (2019) 380–400, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21664250.2019.1609713>.
- [36] M. Heidarzadeh, T.K. Papanthanasou, Y. Fan, H. Bahai, A Practical Approach to Advanced Mathematical Modelling in Civil Engineering, Oxford University Press, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780191888656.001.0001>, 384 pages. ISBN: 9780198854241.
- [37] A.S. Dimakopoulos, A. Guercio, G. Cuomo, Advanced numerical modelling of tsunami wave propagation, transformation and run-up, *Proc. Inst. Civil Eng. - Eng. Comput. Mech.* 167 (3) (2014) 139–151, <https://doi.org/10.1680/eacm.13.00029>.
- [38] D. Istrati, I.G. Buckle, Tsunami loads on straight and skewed bridges—part 2: numerical investigation and design recommendations (No. FHWA-OR-RD-21-13). Oregon. Dept. of Transportation, Res. Section (2021). (Available at https://www.oregon.gov/odot/Programs/ResearchDocuments/Tsunami_Part2_Final.pdf, Accessed Dec. 20, 2025).
- [39] R.K.C. Chan, R.L. Street, A computer study of finite-amplitude water waves, *J. Comput. Phys.* 6 (1) (1970) 68–94.
- [40] I.J. Losada, J.L. Lara, R. Guanche, J.M. Gonzalez-Ondina, Numerical analysis of wave overtopping of rubble mound breakwaters, *Coast. Eng.* 55 (1) (2008) 47–62.
- [41] N.G. Jacobsen, M.R. van Gent, G. Wolters, Numerical analysis of the interaction of irregular waves with two dimensional permeable coastal structures, *Coast. Eng.* 102 (2015) 13–29.
- [42] N. Ahmad, H. Bihs, M.A. Chella, A. Kamath, Ø.A. Arntsen, CFD modeling of arctic coastal erosion due to breaking waves, *Int. J. Offshore Polar Eng.* 29 (01) (2019) 33–41.
- [43] T. Xiang, D. Istrati, S.C. Yim, I.G. Buckle, P. Lomonaco, Tsunami loads on a representative coastal bridge deck: experimental study and validation of design equations, *J. Waterw. Port. Coast. Ocean. Eng.* 146 (5) (2020) 04020022, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WW.1943-5460.0000560](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WW.1943-5460.0000560).

- [44] A. Hasanpour, D. Istrati, I. Buckle, Coupled SPH–FEM modeling of tsunami-borne large debris flow and impact on coastal structures, *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 9 (10) (2021) 1068, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9101068>.
- [45] Hasanpour, A., Istrati, D., & Buckle, I.G. (2022). Multi-physics modeling of tsunami debris impact on bridge decks. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards & Infrastructure, Athens, Greece* (pp. 5–7). EID: 2-s2.0-85137813076, Part of ISSN: 26234513.
- [46] H. von Häfen, C. Krautwald, H. Bihs, N. Goseberg, Dam-break waves' hydrodynamics on composite bathymetry, *Front. Built. Environ.* 8 (2022) 877378.
- [47] D. Di Luccio, P.P.C. Aucelli, G. Di Paola, M. Pennetta, M. Berti, G. Budillon, G. Benassai, An integrated approach for coastal cliff susceptibility: the case study of Procida Island (southern Italy), *Sci. Total Environ.* 855 (2023) 158759.
- [48] H. Zhao, X. Chang, Y. Huang, J. Zhou, Z. Ti, A stability model for sea cliffs considering the coupled effects of sea erosion and rainfall, *Oceans* 6 (3) (2025) 45, <https://doi.org/10.3390/oceans6030045>.
- [49] H. Gao, W. Qian, J. Dong, J. Liu, Machine learning-based reduced-order reconstruction method for flow fields, *Energy Build.* 320 (2024) 114575.
- [50] P. Pant, R. Doshi, P. Bahl, A. Barati Farimani, Deep learning for reduced order modelling and efficient temporal evolution of fluid simulations, *Phys. Fluids* 33 (10) (2021).
- [51] L. Mu, S. He, S. Chen, X. Chen, J. Shi, Y. Zhang, C. Liu, Prediction of bend-pipeline erosion field based on CFD and reduced order method, *Chem. Eng. Process. -Process Intensif.* 213 (2025) 110320.
- [52] D. Meng, H. Yang, S. Yang, Y. Zhang, A.M. De Jesus, J. Correia, S.P. Zhu, Kriging-assisted hybrid reliability design and optimization of offshore wind turbine support structure based on a portfolio allocation strategy, *Ocean Eng.* 295 (2024) 116842.